

Mycelium-based composites: a comparison of material properties depending on the substrate

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Over time, global plastic production has increased significantly, and the persistent demand for plastics has resulted in the plastic waste in landfills, occupying substantial space and contributing to environmental issues [1]. The quest for sustainable products and technologies has given rise to a new type of materials, with mycelium-based composites being a notable addition [2]. Agricultural and wood processing by-products, typically discarded as waste, can be reused for composite materials. By utilizing lignocellulosic waste and harnessing the natural growth of fungi, there is a potential to create an environmentally sustainable biocomposite that could be used to replace plastic [3].

The objective of this research is to produce and investigate the properties of a unique biological composite material using birch plywood sanding dust (PSD) and the mycelium of the basidiomycete *Trametes versicolor*. Three variants were studied in the formation of mycelial composites – PSD with added wheat bran (S1), PSD with added wheat bran and hemp shives (S2), and PSD with added wheat bran and wood chips (S3). For the S1 variant, we also investigated the properties of the material change by prolonging its cultivation time. Our investigation delved into the influence of substrate composition on specimen bending and compression strength, material density and moisture content.

The highest compression properties were observed in variant S1 with an average value of 0.391 MPa, while the best bending strength properties were found in variant S2 with average value of 0.507 MPa. The density of variant S3, averaging 0.279 g/cm³, was slightly higher than that of S1 (0.258 g/cm³) but more than twice that of S2 (0,131 g/cm³). However, both absolute and relative humidity were not significantly different for all variants. In an experiment investigating the effect of cultivation time on material properties, 2 weeks compared to 1 week of cultivation improved bending but decreased compressive properties and material density. Absolute and relative humidity remained stable.

This study reveals that the addition of hemp shives enhances the bending properties of mycelium composite but reduces its compressive strength and density. Substituting hemp shives for wood chips, however, results in improved density. Additionally, only the bending properties exhibit improvement with prolonged cultivation time. Understanding these findings enables tailored material substrate composition for specific applications, emphasizing the potential of repurposing waste materials for sustainable biocomposites.

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References. [1] Sharuddin S. D. A., Abnisa F., Wan Daud W. M. A., Aroua M. K. A review on pyrolysis of plastic wastes. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 115 (2016) 308-326. [2] Alaneme K. K., Anaele J. U., Oke T. M., Kareem S. A., Adediran M., Ajibuwa O. A., Anabaranze Y. O. Mycelium based composites: A review of their bio-fabrication procedures, material properties and potential for green building and construction applications, 83 (2023) 234-250. [3] Girometta C., Picco A. M., Baiguera R. M., Dondi D., Babbini S., Cartabia M., Pellegrini M., Savino E. Physico-Mechanical and Thermodynamic Properties of Mycelium-Based Biocomposites: A Review, 11 (2019) 281.